

RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

Interfacial Behavior of Methane in Methane/*p*-Xylene/Water Systems: First Principles Inspected Using Neutron Imaging and Molecular Dynamics Simulations

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Received: 29 August 2025 | **Revised:** 6 December 2025 | **Accepted:** 20 January 2026

Keywords: adsorption at interface | methane | molecular dynamics simulation | neutron imaging | water

ABSTRACT

Pressurized gases adsorb on the gas-liquid (*g-l*) interfaces, thus reducing the interfacial tension (IFT). Gas-saturated liquid-liquid (*l-l*) emulsions occur in oil and gas wells, possible IFT changes due to saturation remain unclear. We study if the IFT reduction occurs for the model system of methane, *p*-xylene, and water. The neutron imaging (NI) observations of bulk (*g-l-l*) systems at 100 bar provide several quantities simultaneously from each experimental run, e.g., IFT for *g-l* and methane diffusivity for the *p*-xylene rich phase, but does not sensitively provide IFT for the *l-l* interface. The quantities derived for the *p*-xylene-rich phase using NI allows us to calibrate molecular dynamics (MD) simulation, which is used for the predictions of IFT for *l-l*, literature data for binary benzene/water (*l-l*) system are used as the reference. Overall, no, or very minor effect ($\pm 1 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$) on IFT is robustly found up to methane saturation at 100 bar. Variation of partial charges on the *p*-xylene model from zero to quantum calculation-based modulate the fine structure of *p*-xylene/water interface and has small, yet qualitative effect on IFT, resulting in a weak adsorption (-1 mN m^{-1}), or weak depletion ($+1 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$) of methane from *l-l*.

1 | Introduction

The stability of oil-water (oil in water, water in oil) interfaces at low/ambient pressures is known to be influenced by the presence of charged species (e.g., ion-specific effects) and of dissolved gases, while such emulsions are the main waste stream produced by the oil and gas industry [1–5]. For instance, the stability of emulsions containing dissolved gas (air) at atmospheric pressure is lower than that of the vacuum-degassed ones, bridging of the oil droplets in water through coalesced gas microbubbles is likely the key mechanism [6–17]. Oil-water emulsions saturated

by gases at high pressures appear studied less frequently, while their stability is potentially influenced by changes of interfacial tension (IFT) that are inevitably of greater extent than at low pressure. Application-oriented empirical studies focused on the stability and viscosity of emulsions at well conditions (e.g., water in oil saturated with methane at 100 bar) were reported [4, 18, 19]. The complexity of real crude oil, however, complicates the analysis. We study highly controlled systems from methane, *p*-xylene, and water, which are model constituents of crude oil and highly condensable impurities in crude natural gas [20, 21]. The focus is on the first-principle investigation of whether IFT

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changes at comparable conditions as in oil wells due to the system saturation by the dissolved methane.

Pressurized gases (positively) adsorb on *g-l* interfaces and thus reduce IFT, which was observed, for instance, for methane/water [22–24] and methane/*p*-xylene [25] systems, the phenomenon is governed by van der Waals interactions [6]. Interestingly, the surface excess of methane at the methane/water interface reaches a maximum at about 100 bar but decreases at higher pressures and becomes negligible or even negative above 500 bar (0°C–50°C). This nontrivial behavior, which was reproduced in atomistic simulations, is consistent with Gibbs interpretation of the plateau in IFT observed experimentally near 500 bar of methane [23]. To our knowledge, adsorption of dissolved gases on the *l-l* interface was not reported in the available literature.

We combine macroscopic observation of three-phase systems at elevated pressures using neutron imaging (NI) with molecular dynamics (MD) simulations. NI enables the observation of the shapes of the mobile phase interfaces at high pressure [25, 26], as well as the assessment of several physical quantities of the system from each experimental run [26]. These physical quantities are used for the MD model calibration, followed by predictions and molecular-scale analysis of the water/*p*-xylene interface in the presence of dissolved methane at conditions beyond the experimentally accessible region.

2 | Results and Discussion

2.1 | NI Observations, MD Predictions

The time-resolved NI observations of the three-phase system from methane, *p*-xylene, and water provided information on the shape and composition of the liquid bodies (Figure 1).

The processing of the radiographs and bulk-phase modeling provided the IFT (γ) for the two-phase interfaces, methane diffusivity in the *p*-xylene phase (D_A^B), apparent Henry's law constant for methane in the *p*-xylene phase (H), and apparent molar volume of methane in the *p*-xylene phase (V_A^{app}). The so-derived experimental data and literature data are compared below to the predictions derived from MD simulations. As three-phase systems of methane, *p*-xylene, and water show very low solubility for the methane–water and *p*-xylene–water pairs, the system can be considered a set of two-phase systems. Experimental and MD simulation data are listed in the [Supporting Information](#).

The experimentally accessible quantities (listed above) were insensitive to the *p*-xylene saturation with water. Methane diffusivity in the water-saturated *p*-xylene phase (D_A^B) was by $0.8 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ higher (i.e., ca 15%) than that for dry *p*-xylene [27], the experimental uncertainty was $0.4 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. Experimental and MD-simulated diffusivities compared well to the ones predicted using the MD simulation once universal constant k_γ was optimized (Figure 2a), see ref. [25] for definition. Apparent Henry's law constant for methane in *p*-xylene rose, on average, by 5% due to the saturation of the *p*-xylene phase with water (Figure 2b), while the average relative experimental uncertainty was 15%. The respective MD-simulated quantity was overestimated, which originates from the previously reported sensitive

FIGURE 1 | Tomographic reconstructions (obtained using onion-peeling algorithm) of the measuring cell with perdeuterated *p*-xylene ($p\text{-C}_8\text{D}_{10}$) layered over water (10.88 mol.% of H_2O in D_2O) exposed to methane pressure change, all at 7.0°C. Red curves are fits of Young-Laplace equation, grayscale corresponds to the linear coefficient of neutron attenuation, yellow lines show liquids levels. Adapted from reference [26].

propagation of the uncertainty of the excess (residual) chemical potential [25]. The apparent molar volume of methane in *p*-xylene did not change upon saturation with water to within the experimental uncertainty of $5 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ (Figure 2c). Predicted and experimental apparent molar volumes compared well. The predicted IFT for the methane/*p*-xylene interface overestimated the experimental values, the latter having the uncertainty estimated to 2 mN m^{-1} using the Bonferroni method [28], the pressure dependences of both were comparable. They could be well parameterized with a semi-empirical model being the product of the simplified Guggenheim's model of temperature dependence [29] and the model of von Szyszkowski [30] of the concentration dependence of IFT (Figure 2d).

MD-simulated quantities for binary systems for which literature data are available [22, 27, 33–41] are shown in section S1. As a showcase, the MD-predicted methane solubility in water and IFT for the methane/water system are compared to the experimental data by Sachs and Meyn [22] in Figure 3. Beyond the MD predictions used for validation, experimentally inaccessible physical quantities were predicted for the binary systems (Table 1).

IFT for methane/*p*-xylene at atmospheric pressure was insensitive to the saturation by water. Experimental data (NI) were lower than those from the literature, while MD prediction overestimated both and captured the expected dependence on temperature (Figure 4a). In the case of the NI observation of the *p*-xylene/water interface, IFT from the literature was underestimated, IFT decreased with increasing pressure but the experimental uncertainty was too high (16 mN m^{-1} , Figure 4b);

FIGURE 2 | Experimental and MD-predicted quantities for the system methane (A) and *p*-xylene (B) layered over water (C). Data for water-free systems [27] are marked by *. Methane diffusivity D_A^B with $k_\eta = 0.872$ (a), apparent Henry's law constant H (b), apparent molar volume of methane V_A^{app} (c), and IFT γ (d) are plotted against methane pressure, temperature is indicated in the legends. Regressions of simulated [$T \in (283 \text{ K}, 353 \text{ K})$, $p \in (1 \text{ bar}, 100 \text{ bar})$, $x_A \in (0, 0.23)$] and experimental [$T \in (280.2 \text{ K}, 303.2 \text{ K})$, $p \in (1 \text{ bar}, 100 \text{ bar})$, $x_A \in (0, 0.26)$] data are shown. AAD abbreviates Average Absolute Deviation. Literature data shown in the graphs: # methane and *p*-xylene [20], ## methane and *n*-hexane [31], #\\$ methane and benzene [32]. Points are experimental, curves are regressions of simulated data.

FIGURE 3 | Methane molar fraction in a saturated solution calculated from the true Henry's law constant (a) and IFT (b) for the methane/water system as a function of methane (compound A) pressure at 25°C. Curves are regressions of MD-simulated data, points (#) are from the literature [22].

TABLE 1 | Simulated partial molar volumes and diffusivities for binary solutions at the infinite dilution of the indicated component. Data were MD-simulated at 10 and 100 bar, 283.0, 298.0, 313.0, and 353.0 K, see [Supporting Information](#). Regressions (p in bar, T in K, \bar{V} in $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$, $D \times 10^9$ in $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$, $R = 8.31451 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ [42]) fit simulated data to within the indicated AAD. A stands for methane, B is p -xylene, C is water.

System	Regression	AAD
A (dil.), C	$D_A = 1700 \exp \frac{-17200}{R \cdot T} - 170 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot p$	0.15
A (dil.), C	$D_C = 1280 \exp \frac{-15860}{R \cdot T} - 72.8 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot p$	0.05
A (dil.), C	$\bar{V}_A = 37.6 + 2.45 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot (T - 298) - 1.43 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot (T - 298)^2 - 1.58 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot p$	0.65
A (dil.), B	$\bar{V}_A = 47.2 + 0.157 \cdot (T - 298) - 695 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot (T - 298)^2 - 6.33 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot p$	0.63
C (dil.), B	$D_C = 930 \exp \frac{-12700}{R \cdot T} - 10.5 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot p$	0.40
C (dil.), B	$D_B = 402 \exp \frac{-12920}{R \cdot T} - 2.140 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot p$	0.04
C (dil.), B	$\bar{V}_C = 21.9 + 51.8 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot (T - 298) - 418 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot (T - 298)^2 + 266 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot p$	0.23
B (dil.), C	$D_C = 1280 \exp \frac{-15870}{R \cdot T} - 71 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot p$	0.05
B (dil.), C	$D_B = 670 \exp \frac{-1700}{R \cdot T} + 150 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot p$	0.05
B (dil.), C	$\bar{V}_B = 117.6 + 0.161 \cdot (T - 298) - 81.3 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot (T - 298)^2 - 4.52 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot p$	0.4

data were not used for the MD validation. High uncertainty results from the low interface shape sensitivity for high $\gamma/\Delta\rho$ that was reported earlier [26]. The uncertainty could be, in principle, enhanced by using cells of varied inner diameter, leading to the increase of shape sensitivity and also neutron attenuation. In the above, validation of the MD simulation was done for a set of physical quantities, which resulted in shown differences from the reference data and expectable dependences on state variables. The next section presents MD simulation of the p -xylene/water interface, which provides a detailed angstrom-resolution insight into the structure of studied interfaces.

2.2 | Microscopic Insight into Structure of Interfaces

Equilibrium MD simulations provide a microscopic view into the studied system. At the mean-field level, equilibrium density distributions of molecules in the bulk phases and at interfaces can be calculated [43–45]. By performing the simulations of a three-phase system, Figure 5 illustrates that the microscopic model captures the p -xylene/water interface (see sharp density changes at $z = 0$), low vapor pressure of water, virtually no solubility of methane in water, and modest solubility of methane in p -xylene. Moreover, the model provides insight into the density distribution (simulation averaged) at the interfaces, from which surface excess or depletion (most importantly of methane) are determined and changes in IFT are evaluated. It is noteworthy that the methane affinity to individual phases differs enough to be directly visualized in the intrinsic simulation snapshot. The top panel of Figure 5 highlights (denoted by bigger spheres) methane molecules in $\Delta z = 5 \text{ \AA}$ thick slices localized at different phases and interfaces of the system, which is here at equilibrium with the methane pressure of 100 bar.

The correct behavior of the three-phase system model allows us to utilize two-phase systems that are more convenient for quantitative (predictive) modelling of the interface structure and IFT between water and p -xylene. Predictions of other quanti-

ties were shown above. Figure 6 summarizes the results, both macroscopic and structural properties, determined from MD simulation data. First, the temperature dependence of IFT was directly evaluated from the pressure tensor. It is challenging for a simple non-polarizable atomistic p -xylene force field (FF) [46] to simultaneously reproduce both the correct temperature dependence and the correct magnitude of the IFT ($\approx 35 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$ [34, 35]). Figure 6a shows that to reproduce the correct magnitude of IFT, reasonable partial charges on the p -xylene atoms are required (in the order of $\pm 0.15 e$, i.e., from $1.0 \times$ to $0.75 \times$ scaling of charges determined from quantum chemical calculation). However, the temperature dependence of IFT is absent in these models. Only when the charges are reduced to ca $0.5 \times$, the temperature dependence of IFT is recovered. To reach the typical experimental slope $\approx -0.1 \text{ mN m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ [47], partial charges must be reduced by $<0.25 \times$ scaling. However, these models predict too high absolute magnitude of IFT, which is in the range of ≈ 50 – 60 mN m^{-1} (i.e., close to alkane/water IFT [47]). Full details are provided in section S2.

Next, we analyzed the structure of the p -xylene/water interface in the presence of dissolved methane, up to $x_{\text{Me}} = 0.3$ (equivalent to $p_{\text{Me}} = 100 \text{ bar}$) in the p -xylene phase. No significant impact of methane is observed on the structure of p -xylene/water interface as documented in Figure S6 in section S2. In particular, the width of the interface and the mutual solubility of water and p -xylene are unchanged. These results are rather insensitive to the parametrization of the p -xylene molecule. By analyzing the density profile of methane at the p -xylene/water interface, we have found only a marginal effect of methane on IFT ($<1 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$). This observation remains robust with the change to the p -xylene FF (see Section S2). On a qualitative level, however, the choice of p -xylene FF affects the affinity of methane to the interface, shifting from mild depletion (implying $\Delta\gamma > 0$) to mild enrichment ($\Delta\gamma < 0$) of methane at the interface, for polar and nonpolar model of p -xylene, respectively (Figures S6 and S7 in section S2). This minor affinity of methane contrasts with its surface activity at both surfaces, i.e., methane/water and methane/ p -xylene, where the changes of IFT are about 5 – $10 \times$ larger (see comparison in Figure 6b).

FIGURE 4 | Panel a): IFT for the methane (A) and *p*-xylene (B) interface, system layered over water (C). Literature data for water-free systems are marked by * [27], # [39], ## [40], #\$ [41], and #@ [33]. Panel b): IFT for *p*-xylene (B) and water (C) exposed to the indicated pressure of methane (A). Literature *p*-xylene/water systems are marked by & [34], and &#[35].

FIGURE 5 | Illustration of the solution structure in the coexisting phases and at the interfaces in the system of *p*-xylene, water, and methane, $p_{\text{Me}} = 100$ bar and $T = 298$ K. The top panel presents a snapshot of the system composition, where the water phase (thin red lines representation) in the middle left is in contact with *p*-xylene phase (thin cyan lines) in the middle right, both dense liquid phases are surrounded by methane gas (black spheres). The bottom panel presents the equilibrium density profiles of individual components (see the legend) resolved along the *z*-axis (perpendicular to the interfaces). Surface enrichment of methane (denoted by peaks) at methane/water and at methane/*p*-xylene interfaces and depletion from the water/*p*-xylene interface (denoted by decrease of density) are clearly visible. These changes in methane density are sufficient to be visually captured by highlighting methane molecules (bigger black spheres) at different system locations (slice thickness, $\Delta z = 5$ Å).

The surface and interfacial excess of methane are compared in Figure 6c, where the methane concentration in the *p*-xylene phase is overlaid. A prominent peak in the methane *z*-density profile at methane/*p*-xylene surface is observed and quantified by a substantial surface excess of methane (see also Section S5). A similar observation applies to the methane/water interface, for

which results are provided in Figure S14 and in section S3. In contrast, only minor excess or depletion of methane is found at methane/*p*-xylene/water interface, depending on the *p*-xylene FF (see Figure 6c and Figure S6 in section S2).

The quantitative decrease of interfacial activity of methane at methane/*p*-xylene/water interface originates from a tighter packing and lower compressibility of both liquids close to the liquid-liquid interface in comparison with gas-liquid interface. This is supported in Figure S14 in section S5, which compares shapes (widths) of *p*-xylene and water interface, when exposed to methane gas or to the other liquid phase. In contact with water, the *p*-xylene interface significantly narrows (from -0.7 to 0.7 nm with respect to Gibbs dividing surface at gas/*p*-xylene to ca -0.3 to 0.3 nm at water/*p*-xylene) and its density in the subsurface increases (stays close to bulk value), which lowers the capacity for methane excess at this interface. In contrast, the shape and width of the water interface is only weakly affected by the presence of *p*-xylene. The width is approximately -0.3 to 0.3 nm in the gas phase and broadens or narrows by approximately 0.05 nm when *p*-xylene carries full or no partial charges, respectively. These differences in behavior (compressibility) of water and *p*-xylene interfaces reflect the involvement of strong directional electrostatic (H-bond) and weak dispersion interactions (LJ). Due to many-body effects, the existence of internal cavities (or low-density regions) is energetically highly unfavorable in the condensed phase. The packing effects dominate and narrow the transition region at water/*p*-xylene interface. In other words, the low-density gaseous region, which contributes the most to the methane excess at liquid/gas interfaces, is absent at liquid/liquid interface (see Figure 6 and Figure S15 in section S7).

By means of total mass density, Figure S5 in section S2 (right panel) presents a detail view into the fine structure of the water/*p*-xylene interface, which results from the balance of involved forces

FIGURE 6 | MD simulation prediction of IFT for *p*-xylene/water system with changes in temperature (a) or with equilibrium methane gas density (b). The left panel (a) presents the effect of temperature for *p*-xylene models with full (brown triangles, scaling = 1.0) and reduced partial charges (see the legend for scaling). The middle panel (b) presents estimated changes of IFT ($\Delta\gamma$) with concentration of methane in the gas phase (equivalent to p_{Me}) at 283 K (green) and 353 K (blue). Due to the impact of the *p*-xylene FF (for details see Section S2), the shaded area reflects the uncertainty in the IFT prediction. Nevertheless, $\Delta\gamma$ is small when compared to the methane impact on methane/water (black), or methane/*p*-xylene (red) interfaces. The right panel (c) compares the density profiles of methane (black) at methane/*p*-xylene (gas) and methane/*p*-xylene/water interfaces (at 298 K, $p_{\text{Me}} = 100$ bar). The methane densities are aligned in the *p*-xylene phase, which highlights the marginal interfacial activity of methane at methane/*p*-xylene/water interface (comparison to the methane/water interface is provided in Figure S14 in section S6).

(i.e., chemical details, and FF parameterization). Qualitatively, with full or $0.75 \times \text{QM}$ charges the total mass density transitions rather smoothly from *p*-xylene to water density. But, with lower partial charges (from $0.5 \times \text{QM}$ to zero charges) a noticeable dip in total density in the *p*-xylene subsurface region (ca 0.3 nm thick) is observed. With zero partial charges at *p*-xylene, i.e., form the most immiscible water/*p*-xylene system, the decrease in density is as much as 50 kg m^{-3} (i.e., ca 6% of total mass density 850 kg m^{-3}). As documented by Figure S6, methane is enriched in this subsurface region of decreased density, resulting in noticeable interfacial excess, which is, however, quantitatively minor. Note that for a methane particle ($V_{\text{A}}^{\text{app}} = 0.075 \text{ nm}^3$) the 6% decrease in liquid density (i.e., 6% of free volume in 0.3 nm thick subsurface), allows to accommodate only ≈ 0.25 particle/ nm^2 , which is on the scale with the methane surface excess observed in Figure S7 in section S2. The mechanism of the methane excess at the liquid/liquid interface is thus similar in nature to that at liquid/gas interface, but its magnitude is limited due to the crowded nature of the condense phase.

After a thorough computational, structural and theoretical analysis, we can conclude that the surface excess or depletion of methane at such a type of interface (liquid/liquid) as well as the impact on IFT are limited.

3 | Conclusions

Three-phase systems constituted from perdeuterated *p*-xylene ($p\text{-C}_8\text{D}_{10}$) layered over water (10.88 mol.% of H_2O in D_2O) and exposed to pressurized methane (CH_4 , 1.0–101 bar) at 7.0°C – 30.0°C were observed using neutron imaging. This setup enabled the derivation of the time- and space-resolved evolution of concentration and density of the *p*-xylene phase, and thus enabled the derivation of the respective IFT, diffusivity, solubility, and partial molar volume of methane. While IFT for the methane/*p*-

xylene interface was determined within 2 mN m^{-1} , that for the *p*-xylene/water was burdened with the uncertainty of 16 mN m^{-1} .

The experimentally accessible quantities (except IFT for *p*-xylene/water due to high uncertainty) and data available from the literature compared well to the predictions of the optimized MD simulation. MD-based predictions of the experimentally inaccessible quantities, namely, partial molar volumes and diffusivities, were provided. Moreover, molecular-level analysis focused on the pressurized methane distribution in the system showed that the key prerequisite for the surface excess formation is the accessibility of the neighboring phase for the accumulating gas. While methane accumulates at the methane/*p*-xylene and methane/water interfaces to form a thicker layer of adsorbed methane (ca 1.5 nm), a thinner layer of methane (ca 4 Å) is affected to a much smaller extent at the *p*-xylene/water interface. The lack of space for the methane accumulation at the liquid/liquid interface limits its interfacial activity (within $\pm 1 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$). Whether the small accumulation of methane at the *p*-xylene/water interface is positive or negative sensitively depends on the parameterization of the charge distribution within the *p*-xylene molecule, which modulates *p*-xylene-water interaction and impact the fine structure of liquid/liquid interface. While pressurized methane accumulates at its interfaces with liquid *p*-xylene and water, which are model impurities of crude natural gas, it causes minor changes (even an increase) of IFT for the *p*-xylene/water interface.

4 | Experimental Section/Methods

4.1 | Neutron Imaging

NI experiments were performed using the previously reported one-pot method [25, 27, 48]. A cylindrical cell parallel to gravity containing the three-phase system was imaged at the NEUTRA

FIGURE 7 | Simulation setups used in this work. The three-phase slab simulation setup (a), homogeneous liquid phase of *p*-xylene with dissolved methane in contact with water (b), and bulk homogeneous *p*-xylene phase with dissolved methane (c). Methane is represented as blue spheres, *p*-xylene as green, and water as red-white structures.

beamline [49] at Paul Scherrer Institute. A MIDI-box detector system contained a 30 μm -thick $\text{Gd}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}:\text{Tb}$ scintillator screen, and an sCMOS camera (Andor Neo) combined with a 100-mm objective (Zeiss Makro-Planar). Images of 2560 (W) \times 2160 (H) pixels in size were collected, the estimated spatial resolution is better than 80 micrometers, isotropic pixel pitch equaled 20.3 μm . Two cells (titanium alloy Ti-6Al-4V, inner diameter 9.0 ± 0.1 mm) were imaged simultaneously. One contained methane (CH_4 , PanGas, 4.5), water (10.88 mol.% of H_2O in D_2O , Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, 99.93 atom-% D), and *p*-xylene (*p*- C_8D_{10} , Armar, 99.59 atom-% D), which is the focus of the current work. The other cell contained methane (CH_4) and *p*-xylene (*p*- C_8D_{10}); results for the water-free system were reported elsewhere [27]. Isotopically labeled compounds were used because of the significant difference in neutron cross-sections of protium (H) and deuterium (D) [50]. We used this difference to adjust the contrast among the liquid phases, and to quantify the dissolved methane in the *p*-xylene phase (Figure 1). Experiments were initiated by the steep change of methane pressure in the cells from atmospheric to a preset value. Liquid perdeuterated *p*-xylene (*p*- C_8D_{10}) was layered over water (10.88 \pm 0.05 mol.% of H_2O in D_2O) in the cell [25, 27, 48] maintained at a constant temperature, and exposed to a methane (CH_4) pressure step at the zero time. The onion-peeling algorithm [51] was used to provide the tomographic reconstructions at the central plane of the sample. Further details on the experiment, modeling, and processing of the radiographies were described earlier [25, 27]. Briefly, the cells with the two liquid layers were exposed to pressurized methane, and their neutron radiographies (projection) were collected over time. The central-plane tomographic reconstructions were then calculated from the radiographies and used to retrieve information on the shapes and positions of the phase interfaces and composition. Modeling was based on the Young-Laplace equation, Fick's second law, and Euler's first theorem for homogeneous functions.

4.2 | Molecular Dynamics

Three-phase systems composed of methane (A), *p*-xylene (B), and water (C) were studied. The used MD simulations rely on TIP4P/2005 water model [52] and all-atom parameterization of *p*-xylene from LigParGen based on Lennard-Jones OPLS-AA parameters with 1.14*CM1A or 1.14*CM1A-LBCC partial atomic charges [53–55] with a cut-off set to 2.0 nm. The long-range

electrostatics was accounted for by particle mesh Ewald (PME) summation with a grid spacing of 0.16 nm in conjunction with a tinfoil boundary condition as implemented in GROMACS [56]. This approach was demonstrated to reproduce the phase behavior of neat liquids, presenting a starting point for simulations of mixtures at multi-phase coexistence. MD simulations were conducted using the GROMACS 2024 simulation package [57], the timestep was 2 fs and sampling period 1 ps. In all cases, periodic boundary conditions (PBC) in 3D space were applied. The simulated systems were divided into groups based on the number of co-existing phases.

The first set of simulations included three-phase systems with an explicit presence of three different interfaces, i.e., the slab simulation setup (Figure 7a). These simulations mimic the (idealized) experimental design and prove the ability of MD simulations to model multiphase systems. This setup enabled the evaluation of equilibrium density profiles across the interfaces (solubilities). A rectangular cuboid with equilibrium side lengths of ca $4.1 \times 4.1 \times 30$ nm contained 500 *p*-xylene molecules, 4000 water and 300–1500 methane molecules based on previously calculated Henry's law constants (to have a stable gas phase of a reasonable size), which were distributed in separated regions at the start of the simulation utilizing the PACKMOL package [58]. The width of water and *p*-xylene phases was ca 6–7 nm, the remaining space represented the methane gas phase. In analogy to our previous study on two-phase systems from methane and *p*-xylene [25], energy minimization was followed by the slab simulation for 60 ns in an isothermal-semi-isobaric NpT ensemble (compressible in *z*-direction only). The first 30 ns were taken out as an equilibration, and the last 30 ns were used for analysis. All three-phase simulations were performed with three separate V-rescale thermostats [59] ($\tau_T = 0.5$ ps) used for separate temperature coupling of methane, *p*-xylene, and water and a C-rescale barostat ($\tau_p = 2.0$ ps) [60].

The second set of simulations was focused on the two-phase (slab) systems and contained liquid/liquid and gas/liquid interfaces. Namely, interfaces *p*-xylene/water, (*p*-xylene saturated with methane)/water, gaseous methane/liquid water, and gaseous methane/liquid *p*-xylene (Figure 7b). All these simulations were 40 ns long, and were performed in an isothermal-semi-isobaric NpT ensemble (compressible in *z*-direction only). The first 20 ns were used for equilibration, followed by 20 ns for analysis. All

two-phase simulations were performed with separate V-rescale thermostats [25, 59] ($\tau_T = 0.5$ ps) used for separate temperature coupling of individual components and C-rescale barostat [60] ($\tau_p = 2.0$ ps). We note that a series of *p*-xylene parameterizations (of different polarity) was employed for the quantitative modelling of *p*-xylene/water IFT (for details see sections S1–S7).

The third set of simulations was focused on the bulk properties. Bulk simulations (Figure 7c) represent an efficient and reliable method for the determination of diffusion, viscosity, density, true Henry's law constant, chemical potentials, or local solution structure [25]. Bulk simulations were performed in the isobaric-isothermal (NpT) ensemble with V-rescale thermostat ($\tau_T = 0.5$ ps) and C-rescale barostat ($\tau_p = 2$ ps). The simulation was conducted in two parts, 20 ns for equilibration, and 20 ns for analysis.

Funding

M.M., T-M.D., J.Š., J.L., J.H., P.T., and O.V. acknowledge the financial support obtained from the Czech Science Foundation (GACR) and Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF), GACR number 23-04741K, SNSF number 200021E_213197. M.M. and J.Š. acknowledge support from the grant of Specific university research – grant No A1_FCHI_2024_001, A1_FCHI_2025_001. J.H. and M.M. acknowledge the support from the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic within the projects “The Energy Conversion and Storage”, project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617, Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research, and “e-INFRA CZ” (ID: 90254). This work is based on experiments performed at the NEUTRA thermal neutron imaging beamline, Swiss spallation neutron source SINQ, Paul Scherrer Institute, Villigen, Switzerland.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article. Primary simulation data (parameters, trajectories) are available at Zenodo under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15438018>.

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Supporting Information

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Supporting file: admi70419-sup-0001-SuppMat.docx.